

OMMAVIY-MADANIY TADBIRLAR TUSHUNCHASI VA TARIXI

Nurniyazov Atabek Batirbay uli

Tlewnazarova Ziyuargul Baynazar qizi

Tajimurtaova Shaxnoza Saqinbaevana

(Ilmiy rahbar)

Karakalpak State University named after Berdak.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11218476>

Anotatsiya. Bu maqolada badiiy-ommaviy tadbirlar printsiplari, badiiy-ommaviy tadbirlar funksiyalari, ommaviylik va ixtiyoriylik printsiplari, axborot va badiiylikni uyg'unlashtirish printsiplari, jamoatchilikning tashabbuskorlik va havaskorligi printsiplari haqida soz etilgan.

Kalit sozlar: Badiiy-ommaviy, tadbirlar, ijtimoiy-madaniy, madaniy-ma'rifiy.

CONCEPT AND HISTORY OF PUBLIC CULTURAL EVENTS

Abstract. This article describes the principles of artistic and public events, the functions of artistic and public events, the principles of publicity and voluntariness, the principles of combining information and art, the principles of initiative and amateurism of the public.

Key words: Artistic-public, events, social-cultural, cultural-educational.

КОНЦЕПЦИЯ И ИСТОРИЯ МАССОВЫХ КУЛЬТУРНЫХ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ

Аннотация. Рассмотрены принципы проведения публичных художественных мероприятий, функции публичных художественных мероприятий, принципы публичности и добровольности, принципы соединения информации и искусства, принципы инициативы и дилетантизма публики.

Ключевые слова: Художественно-общественные, мероприятия, социально-культурные, культурно-просветительские.

While learning the theory of artistic and public events, it is important to know their essence and place in social and cultural life, it is also important to study their unique principles and functions (tasks) on a scientific basis.

The specific principles of artistic and public events are the main source of guidance in their organization.

The principle is "the basic rule of theory, teaching, science and the like"; "laws and regulations used as a basis for activity". A principle is a rule that must be followed.

Since artistic and public events are a part of ideology, cultural and educational activities, they are primarily subject to general ideological principles. These include:

1. The principle of idealism and nationalism.
2. Scientific principle.
3. The principle of connection with life, construction practice.
4. Combat principle.
5. To different groups and classes of the population principle of differential approach.

These general ideological principles play the role of the main charter in the activities of culture and art institutions that carry out all ideological work, including the organization of artistic and public events.

At the same time, there are specific principles of cultural and educational work, including public events. They are created on the basis of the essence of cultural and educational work, the role they play in life. In turn, these specific principles create the main tasks of cultural and educational work and the rules of organization of all forms of work.

1. The specific principles of cultural and educational work, including artistic and public events, are as follows:

2. The principle of popularity and voluntariness. It is optional to come to events organized in cultural and educational institutions. No one can be forced to participate in events. Workers can choose the activities they like and be their participants. Events must be popular and interesting for everyone. To achieve this, the organized activities should be of a high level and meet the basic spiritual needs and requirements of the population.

3. The principle of initiative and amateurism of the public. Events are organized only for and with the participation of local residents. In professional collectives, performances are prepared by professional performers - actors, soloists, dancers, and in cultural and educational institutions, the participants and members of events are mainly public initiators and amateurs. That's why it is necessary to widely involve initiative people and members of artistic amateur collectives in organizing the event and use their activities effectively.

4. The principle of enriching and growing the spiritual image of a person. It is known that a person cannot fully satisfy his needs during the main work process and outside of it. In this regard, cultural and educational institutions, including various events held in them, can help. For this, it is necessary to find out what activities the population is engaged in during their free time, what areas they are interested in and what they need, and organize special events based on certain requirements.

5. The principle of combining information and art (informational logic and emotional imagery). The public is given a certain level of information and knowledge at cultural and public

events. They should be understandable, artistically perfect and impressive in order to interest the population more. For this purpose, it is necessary to convey the information to the public in a more artistic and emotional image form, with extensive use of effective means.

6. The principle of beautifying the content of the recreation process. Events are mainly organized during the free time of workers and special forms of rest are given to them. In order for workers to have a good rest, events should be organized based on aesthetic enrichment and beauty laws. Beautiful, beautiful, artistic-aesthetic decoration of the place of the event, the form of the organized event, its content, actions and words will have a great effect.

Creative assimilation of the specific principles of general ideological and cultural-educational works mentioned above serves as the main scientific weapon for the organizers of artistic and public events.

The main functions of public art events are based on their general and specific principles.

By "function" we understand the tasks performed by any institution, person or thing within the scope of activity.

Just as every state institution has its own scope of work, cultural and educational institutions also have their own activities and tasks. Since artistic and public events are one of the main areas of cultural and educational institutions, first of all, their functions should be performed with a creative approach in their own way.

Cultural and educational institutions perform the following main functions (tasks) in their work:

- Providing continuous education to the public, continuous and regular improvement of their knowledge.
- Involve the public in amateur creativity, increase their cultural and social activity and initiative.
- Meaningful organization of workers' rest.

These functions are common to all activities and fields of cultural and educational institutions. But in each of his activities, these functions are used in a unique way. In some activities, for example, in the activities of the public university, the first function is in the organization of lectures, oral agitation and propaganda work, in other activities (for example, in the development of amateur creativity), the second function, in some others, including the organization of artistic and public events, the third function is important.

This function is used in artistic and public events, based on its essence, in a specific order.

They are as follows:

1. The function of organizing workers' rest. It is known that working people often come to

public events tired after work. For this reason, all events should serve as meaningful recreation for them. If all events create conditions for public recreation and artistic-aesthetic pleasure, then it can be said that the work has been done according to the purpose.

Other functions of cultural and educational institutions, i.e. providing knowledge to the public and organizing amateur creativity, are directly related to the recreation of workers in public events.

2. The function of providing information and knowledge to the public. This unique function is a modified form of the first function specific to the activities of cultural and educational institutions, adapted to public events. Continuous systematic education and imparting knowledge in artistic and public events is a complex process.

The process of continuous education can be carried out by means of verbal agitation and propaganda, including public university classes, lectures, and thematic readings. This task can be performed by one of the forms of artistic and public events - oral magazines, and all other cultural and public events can provide information and knowledge specific to the topic. The main requirement of the process of providing information and knowledge in artistic and public events is that it is necessary to avoid familiar knowledge and use new and original information. In order to use such information, special reference books, encyclopedias, institutional, collective farm-state farm and personal archive materials will be used, and preparation of the event based on them will be effective.

The function of attracting the public to artistic amateur creativity. Of course, artistic and public events cannot exist without amateur creativity. The activity of all people participating in the preparation of the event is, without a word, a form of artistic creativity. But when we say "Involvement of the public in amateur creativity", we should understand not only the activities of the organizers of the event, but also the activation of the public who came as spectators, turning them into participants of the general action.

In many forms of artistic and public work, especially in holidays and folk traditions, there are ample facilities for this process. In the process of preparing cultural and public events, it is important to refer to the specific organizational features of a certain form of work in the performance of the above-mentioned function. Because these functions are not used equally when organizing different forms of work. In some forms, more information is given, some serve mainly for recreation, and others help to participate in a more cultural and creative process.

REFERENCES

1. B.Sayfullayev. «Tomosha san'ati tarixi va nazariyasi». T., 2014.

2. M.Umarov. «Estrada va ommaviy tomoshalar tarixi». T., «Yangi asr avlodi», 2009.
3. F.Ahmedov. «Ommaviv bayramlar rejissurasi asoslari». T.: «Aloqachi». 2008.
4. Tajimuratova S. CONCEPT OF FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL CULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 1. – С. 251-254.
5. Tajimuratova S. FORMATION OF STUDENTS'SKILLS OF INDEPENDENT PERFORMANCE THROUGH THE TEACHING OF ART HISTORY //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 10. – С. 841-849.
6. Saginbaevna T. S. FORMATION OF STUDENTS'SKILLS OF INDEPENDENT PERFORMANCE THROUGH THE TEACHING OF ART HISTORY //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – T. 9. – С. 386-392.
7. Sag'inbaevna T. S. Cultural Life in Uzbekistan during the Years of Independence //Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity. – 2023. – T. 18. – С. 39-41.
8. Tajimuratova S. FORMATION OF STUDENTS'SKILLS OF INDEPENDENT PERFORMANCE THROUGH THE TEACHING OF ART HISTORY //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 10. – С. 841-849.
9. Jiyanmuratova Gulnoz. Sotsiologiya tarixi. – T.: Innovatsiya-Ziyo, 2020. – 466 b. / https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=fdboTmYAAAJ&citation_for_view=fdboTmYAAAAAJ:W7OEmFMy1HYC
10. Saginbaevna T. S. Management and study of culture and art. – 2022.
11. Тажимуратова Ш. С. САНЪАТШУНОСЛИК ФАНЛАРИНИ ЎҚИТИШ ОРҚАЛИ ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ МУСТАҚИЛ ИШЛАШ КЎНИКМАЛАРИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ. – 2023.
12. Tajimuraova S. S. INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS IN MANAGEMENT //Journal of Integrated Education and Research. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 5. – С. 509-511.
13. Tajimuratova S. BASQARIW DÁREJESIN ILIMIY DÁREJEDE RAWAJLANDIRIW //NRJ. – 2024. – T. 1. – №. 2. – С. 24-27.
14. Tajimuraova S. S. INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS IN MANAGEMENT //Journal of Integrated Education and Research. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 5. – С. 509-511.
15. Saginbaevna T. S. FORMATION OF STUDENTS'SKILLS OF INDEPENDENT PERFORMANCE THROUGH THE TEACHING OF ART HISTORY //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – T. 9. – С. 386-392.

16. Тажимуратова Ш. С. САНЪАТШУНОСЛИК ФАНЛАРИНИ ЎҚИТИШ ОРҚАЛИ ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ МУСТАҚИЛ ИШЛАШ КЎНИКМАЛАРИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ. – 2023.
17. Shaxnoza T., Rayhan K. JOYBARLARDIŃ SHÓLKEMLESTIRIWSHI STRUKTURALARI //NEW RENASSAINCE CONFERENCE. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 124-128.